

Evaluation of Voltage Stability of Transmission line with P-V curved and V-Q curved Analysis

By: 1. Bill N. Nunneh 2. Rudra Lal Adhikari

Abstract: The inconsistency present in a transmission line tends to have a cascading collapse and different types of failure in the transmission line of a power system which impact the power transfer capability of the line. In this paper we used **MATLAB** coding to plot the real power and the reactive power with voltage. We want to predict what happens to the stability of a power system before a cascading collapse.

Introduction

At any point of time, a power system operating condition should be stable, meeting various operational criteria, and it should also be secure in the event of any credible contingency. Present day power systems are being operated closer to their stability limits due to economic and environmental constraints. Maintaining a stable and secure operation of a power system is therefore a very important and challenging issue. Voltage instability has been given much attention by power system researchers and planners in recent years, and is being regarded as one of the major sources of power system insecurity. Voltage instability phenomena are the ones in which the receiving end voltage decreases well below its normal value and does not come back even after setting restoring mechanisms such as VAR compensators, or continues to

oscillate for lack of damping against the disturbances. Voltage collapse is the process by which the voltage falls to a low, unacceptable value as a result of an avalanche of events accompanying voltage instability [1]. Once associated with weak systems and long lines, voltage problems are now also a source of concern in highly developed networks as a result of heavier loading. The main factors causing voltage instability in a power system are now well explored and understood [1-13]. A brief introduction to the basic concepts of voltage stability and some of the conventional methods of voltage stability analysis are presented in this chapter. Graphical results are shown using **Matlab** on test power systems are presented to illustrate the problem of voltage stability and the conventional methods to analyze the problem. Limitations of conventional methods of voltage stability analysis are pointed.

Classification of voltage stability

The time span of a disturbance in a power system, causing a potential voltage instability problem, can be classified into short-term and long-term. The corresponding voltage stability dynamics is called short-term and long-term dynamics respectively. Automatic voltage regulators, excitation systems, turbine and governor dynamics fall in this short-term or ‘transient’ time scale, which is typically a few seconds. Induction motors, electronically operated loads and HVDC interconnections also fall in this category. If the system is stable, short-term disturbance dies out and the system enters a slow long-term dynamics. Components operating in the long-term time frame are transformer tap changers, limiters, boilers etc. Typically, this time frame is for a few minutes to tens of minutes. A voltage stability problem in the long-term time frame is mainly due to the large electrical distance between the generator and the load, and thus depends on the design of the system [1-5]. Examples of short-term or transient voltage instability can be found in the instability caused by rotor angle imbalance or loss of synchronism [1]. There is not much scope for operator intervention in transient voltage instability. Long-term voltage instability (or mid-term or post-transient, as it is sometimes called) problems can occur in heavily loaded systems where the electrical distance is large between the generator and the load. The instability may be triggered by high power imports from remote generating stations, a sudden large

disturbance, or a large load buildup (such as morning or afternoon pickup). Operator intervention may be possible if the time scale is long enough. Timely application of reactive power compensation or load shedding may prevent this type of voltage instability. From the point of view of techniques used to analyze the voltage stability, it is often useful to categorize the problem into small-disturbance and large-disturbance voltage stability [2]. Small disturbance or steady state voltage stability deals with the situation when the system is subjected to a small perturbation, such that the system can be analyzed by linearizing around the pre-disturbance operating point. Steady state stability analysis is helpful in getting a qualitative picture of the system. Examples of steady state stability can be found in power systems experiencing gradual change in load. Large-disturbance stability deals with larger disturbances such as loss of generation, loss of line etc. To analyze the large-disturbance stability, one has to capture the system dynamics for the whole time frame of the disturbance. A suitable model of the system has to be assumed and a detailed dynamic analysis has to be carried out in order to get a clear picture of the stability.

Voltage stability of a simple 2-bus system

The basic concept of voltage stability can be explain with the aid of a simple 2-bus system shown in fig. 1. The load is of constant power. The real power transfer from bus 1 to bus 2 is given by the equation;

$$P = \frac{EV}{X} \sin \delta \quad 1$$

The reactive power transfer from bus 1 to bus 2 is given also by;

$$Q = -\frac{V^2}{X} + \frac{EV}{X} \cos \delta \quad 2$$

Where, $E = E \angle \delta$ is voltage of bus 1, $V = V \angle 0$ is the voltage at bus 2, X = impedance of the line with negligible resistance, and δ = power angle.

Fig.1. 2-bus test system

Normalizing the terms in eq(1) and eq(2) with $v = V/E$, $p = P.X/E^2$ and $q = Q.X/E^2$, one obtains,

$$p = v \sin \delta \quad 3$$

$$q = -v^2 + v \cos \delta \quad 4$$

Squaring the two equations above and rearranging,

$$v^2 (\sin^2 \delta + \cos^2 \delta) = p^2 + (q + v^2)^2$$

$$\text{or, } v^2 + v^2 (2q - 1) + (p^2 + q^2) = 0 \quad 5$$

Positive real solutions of v from eq(5) are given by

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} - q} \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{4} - p^2 - q} \quad 6$$

Tools for voltage stability analysis

Different methods exist in the literature for carrying out a steady state voltage stability analysis. The conventional methods can be broadly classified into the following types

1. P-V curved method.
2. V-Q curved method and reactive power reserve.

3. Methods based on singularity of power flow Jacobian matrix at the point of voltage collapse.

4. Continuation power flow method.

In this paper we concentrate mainly on the P-V curved, V-Q curved, and the power flow Jacobian matrix at the point of voltage collapse.

P-V curved method

Figure 2: Normalized P-V curves for the 2-bus test system

This is one of the widely used methods of voltage stability analysis. This gives the available amount of active power margin before the point of voltage instability. For radial systems, the voltage of the critical bus is monitored against the changes in real power consumption. For large meshed networks, P can be the total active load in the load area and V can be the voltage of the critical or representative bus. Real power transfer through a transmission interface or interconnection also can be studied by this method. For a simple two-bus system as shown in Figure 1 eq(6) gives real solutions of v^2 , provided $(1 - 4q - 4p^2) \geq 0$.

Assuming a constant power factor load such that $q/p = k$ (constant), the inequality can be expressed as,

$$p \leq \frac{1}{2}((1+k^2)^{1/2} - k) \quad 7$$

For values of 'p' satisfying (1.7), there are two solutions of v as follows:

$$v_1 = (1/2 - p_1k + (1/4 - p_1k - p_1^2)^{1/2})^{1/2} \quad 8$$

$$\text{and } v_2 = (1/2 - p_2k - (1/4 - p_2k - p_2^2)^{1/2})^{1/2} \quad 9$$

For real values of v1 and v2, the terms under the square roots should be positive. Hence,

$$(1/2 - pk - (1/4 - pk - p^2)^{1/2}) \geq 0 \text{ or,}$$

$$p^2 (k^2 + 1) \geq 0 \quad 10$$

Also we can see that eq(7) is the inequality that determines the maximum value of p. Thus, representing the load as a constant power factor type, with a suitably chosen power factor, the active power margin can be computed from eq(7). For different values of load power factors, i.e., for different corresponding values of 'k', the normalized values of load active power are shown in the graph above. In practice, it is possible to find the Thevenin equivalent of any system with respect to the bus under consideration. It is to be noted that the generators are rescheduled at each step of change of the load. Some of the generators may hit the reactive power limit. The network topology may keep changing with respect to the critical bus, with change in the loading, thereby reducing the accuracy of the method. This method works well in the case of an infinite bus and isolated load scenario [9-16].

V-Q curve method and reactive power reserve

Figure 3. Normalized V-Q curves for the 2-bus test system

The V-Q curve method is one of the most popular ways to investigate voltage instability problems in power systems during the post transient period. Unlike the P-V curve method, it doesn't require the system to be represented as two-bus equivalent. Voltage at a test bus or critical bus is plotted against reactive power at that bus. A fictitious synchronous generator with zero active power and no reactive power limit is connected to the test bus. The power-flow program is run for a range of specified voltages with the test bus treated as the generator bus. Reactive power at the bus is noted from the power flow solutions and plotted against the specified voltage. The operating point corresponding to zero reactive power represents the condition when the fictitious reactive power source is removed from the test bus. Voltage security of a bus is closely related to the available reactive power reserve, which can be easily found from the V-Q curve of the bus under consideration. The reactive power margin is the MVAR distance between the operating point and either the nose point of the V-Q curve or the point where capacitor characteristics at the bus are tangent to

the V-Q curve [11]. Stiffness of the bus can be qualitatively evaluated from the slope of the right portion of the V-Q curve. The greater the slope is, the less stiff is the bus, and therefore the more vulnerable to voltage collapse it is. Weak busses in the system can be determined from the slope of V-Q curve. For the simple two-bus system shown in the Figure, equations of V-Q curves for constant power loads can be derived as follows. From eq(3) the power angle δ is computed for specified active power and used in eq(4). For a range of values of voltage and different active power levels, normalized V-Q curves are shown in Figure. The critical point or nose point of the characteristics corresponds to the voltage where dQ/dV becomes zero. If the minimum point of the V-Q curve is above the horizontal axis, then the system is reactive power deficient. Additional reactive power sources are needed to prevent a voltage collapse. In Figure 3, curves for $p=0.25$ and $p=0.75$ signify reactive power deficient busses.

Method based on singularity of power-flow Jacobian matrix at the point of voltage collapse

A number of methods have been proposed in the literature that uses the fact that the power flow Jacobian matrix becomes singular at the point of voltage collapse. Modal analysis [2, 5, 14] of the Jacobian matrix is another good method.

Modal analysis

For a $(n \times n)$ square matrix A , left and right eigenvectors are defined as follows:

$$Ax = \lambda x \quad 11$$

$$yA = \lambda y \quad 12$$

where λ = eigenvalue of the matrix A , x ($n \times 1$) = right eigenvector, y ($1 \times n$) = left eigenvector.

The characteristic equation of both eq(11) and eq(12) is,

$$\det (A-\lambda I) = 0 \quad 13$$

The solution of eq(13), i.e., $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n$ are the eigenvalues of A . For different eigenvalues λ_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, the right and left eigenvectors are defined as, x_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$ and y_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$. In matrix form, the right eigenvector matrix, $X = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$ and the left eigenvector matrix, $Y = [y_1^T, y_2^T, \dots, y_n^T]^T$. It can be shown that, x_j and y_i are orthogonal, such that,

$$y_i \cdot x_j = 0, \quad \forall i \neq j$$

$$\neq 0, \quad \forall i = j$$

In practice, eigenvectors are normalized so that

$$y_i \cdot x_i = 1$$

$$x_i = 1, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, n.$$

$$\text{Hence, } Y \cdot X = I, \text{ or, } Y = X^{-1} \quad 14$$

$$\text{Now, } A \cdot X = [\lambda_{1 \times 1} \lambda_{2 \times 2} \dots \lambda_{n \times n}] = X \cdot \Lambda \quad 15$$

where,

$$\Lambda = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \lambda_n \end{bmatrix}$$

or

$$A = X \Lambda X^{-1} = X \Lambda Y$$

Therefore, we can write power flow equations in matrix as follows;

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta P \\ \Delta Q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} J_{pq} & J_{pv} \\ J_{q\delta} & J_{pq} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \delta \\ \Delta V \end{bmatrix} \quad 17$$

ΔP and ΔQ are the changes in the real and reactive powers respectively, $\Delta\delta$ and ΔV are the deviations in bus voltage angles and bus voltage magnitudes respectively.

For calculating V-Q sensitivities, one can assume $\Delta P = 0$

Hence,

$$J_{p\delta} \cdot \Delta\delta + J_{pV} \cdot \Delta V = 0$$

or,

$$\Delta\delta = -J_{p\delta}^{-1} \cdot J_{pV} \cdot \Delta V \quad 18$$

Now,

$$\Delta Q = J_{q\delta} \cdot \Delta\delta + J_{qV} \cdot \Delta V = J_{q\delta}(-J_{p\delta}^{-1} \cdot J_{pV}) \cdot \Delta V + J_{qV} \cdot \Delta V = J_R \cdot \Delta V \text{ where,}$$

$$J_R = J_{qV} - J_{q\delta} \cdot J_{p\delta}^{-1} \cdot J_{pV}$$

$$\text{Hence, } \Delta V = J_R^{-1} \Delta Q \quad 19$$

Now, assuming $J_R = A$ and using (16) one gets, $J_R = X \Lambda Y$

or, $J_R^{-1} = Y^{-1} \Lambda^{-1} X^{-1} = X \Lambda^{-1} Y$ Using (19), $\Delta V = X \Lambda^{-1} Y \Delta Q$ [since, $X=Y^{-1}$]

$$\text{Hence, } v_m = \Lambda^{-1} q_m$$

where, v_m = vector of modal voltage variation q_m = vector of modal reactive power variation Now,

$$\Lambda^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \lambda_n \end{bmatrix}$$

Thus, $v_{mi} = \lambda_i^{-1} q_{mi}$, $\forall i = 1, \dots, n$ For any i , if $\lambda_i > 0$, then the variation of v_{mi} and q_{mi} are in the same direction and the system is voltage stable. When $\lambda_i < 0$ for any i , the system is voltage unstable.

Conclusion

An increase in 'p' or 'q' both brings the system closer to a maximum power point. An increase in 'p' or 'q' beyond the maximum power point makes the voltage unstable. In a real power system, voltage instability is caused by a combination of many additional factors which include the transmission capability of the network, generator reactive power, voltage control limits, voltage sensitivity of the load, characteristic of reactive compensation devices, and action of voltage control devices such as transformer under load tap changers (ULTCs).

MATLAB CODE

```

%% Plot of Voltage vs active power;
k1 = 1;
p = ((1+k1^2)^(1/2) - k1) / 2;
p1 = [0:0.00001:p];
v1 = (1/2 - p1.*k1 + (1/4 - p1.*k1 - p1.^2).^(1/2)).^(1/2);
v2 = (1/2 - p1.*k1 - (1/4 - p1.*k1 - p1.^2).^(1/2)).^(1/2);
plot(p1, v1, 'k')
hold on;
plot(p1, v2, 'r');
hold on;
k1 = 0.75;
p = ((1+k1^2)^(1/2) - k1) / 2;
p1 = [0:0.00001:p];
v1 = (1/2 - p1.*k1 + (1/4 - p1.*k1 - p1.^2).^(1/2)).^(1/2);
v2 = (1/2 - p1.*k1 - (1/4 - p1.*k1 - p1.^2).^(1/2)).^(1/2);
plot(p1, v1, 'k')
hold on;
plot(p1, v2, 'r')
hold on;
k1 = 0.5;
p = ((1+k1^2)^(1/2) - k1) / 2;
p1 = [0:0.00001:p];
v1 = (1/2 - p1.*k1 + (1/4 - p1.*k1 - p1.^2).^(1/2)).^(1/2);
v2 = (1/2 - p1.*k1 - (1/4 - p1.*k1 - p1.^2).^(1/2)).^(1/2);

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```

plot(p1,v1,'k')
hold on;
plot(p1,v2,'r')
hold on;
k1 = 0.25;
p=((1+k1^2)^(1/2)-k1)/2;
p1=[0:0.00001:p];
v1 = (1/2-p1.*k1+(1/4-p1.*k1-
p1.^2).^(1/2)).^(1/2);
v2 = (1/2-p1.*k1-(1/4-p1.*k1-
p1.^2).^(1/2)).^(1/2);
plot(p1,v1,'k')
hold on;
plot(p1,v2,'r')
hold on;
k1 = 0.00;
p=((1+k1^2)^(1/2)-k1)/2;
p1=[0:0.00001:p];
v1 = (1/2-p1.*k1+(1/4-p1.*k1-
p1.^2).^(1/2)).^(1/2);
v2 = (1/2-p1.*k1-(1/4-p1.*k1-
p1.^2).^(1/2)).^(1/2);
text(0.2,0.5,'k=1.00');
text(0.25,0.60,'k=0.75');
text(0.29,0.70,'k=0.50');
text(0.38,0.66,'k=0.25');
text(0.50,0.73,'k=0.00');
text(0.64,0.81,'k=-0.25');
text(0.81,0.95,'k=-0.50');
text(0.90,1.23,'k=-0.75');

hold on
p=0.25;
v=[p:0.01:1.5];
x=p./v;
delta=real(asind(x));
q=-(-(v.*v) +v.*(cosd(delta)));
plot(v,q)
hold on
p=00;
v=[p:0.01:1.5];
x=p./v;
delta=real(asind(x));
q=-(-(v.*v) +v.*(cosd(delta)));
plot(v,q);
grid on;
xlabel('voltage,v');
ylabel('reactive power,q');
text(1,1,'p=1.00');
text(0.75,0.5625,'p=0.75');
text(0.5,0.25,'p=0.50');
text(0.25,0.0625,'p=0.25');
text(0.01,-0.0099,'p=0.00');

```

```

%%Plot of Reactive Power vs voltage;

```

```

p=1;
v=[p:0.01:1.5];
x=p./v;
delta=asind(x);
q=-(-(v.*v) +v.*(cosd(delta)));
plot(v,q)
hold on
p=0.75;
v=[p:0.01:1.5];
x=p./v;
delta=real(asind(x));
q=-(-(v.*v) +v.*(cosd(delta)));
plot(v,q)
hold on
p=0.50;
v=[p:0.01:1.5];
x=p./v;
delta=real(asind(x));
q=-(-(v.*v) +v.*(cosd(delta)));
plot(v,q)

```

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